

Efficacy of *Akkermansia Muciniphila* as a Prognostic Indicator of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Narrative Review.

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Abstract:**Background:**

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder characterized by absolute or relative insulin deficiency. Complications of type 2 DM (T2DM) can induce gut dysbiosis. This causes decrease in the number of beneficial bacteria and induce inflammation, leading to insulin resistance. *Akkermansia muciniphila* is a gram-negative anaerobic bacterium which is present as a commensal in the human gut. It stimulates the secretion of incretin hormones which increase insulin secretion from the beta cells of pancreas. The primary objective of this literature review is to assess the efficacy of *Akkermansia muciniphila* in the prognosis of diabetes mellitus.

Methods:

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were identified based on a modified version of the PICO framework (Population, Intervention, Control and Outcome) Both randomised and non-randomised studies were included. The search strategy targeted research gaps in interventional research associated with *Akkermansia muciniphilla* and type 2 diabetes. An extensive search was conducted on databases such as PubMed, Semantic Scholar and CrossRef from 20/08/2025 till date. A total of 20 articles were included in the review.

Conclusion:

Results of included studies showed that *Akkermansia muciniphilla* maintains the integrity of the intestinal wall by reducing inflammation. In addition, it reduces endotoxin secretion, gluconeogenesis and lipogenesis. Therefore, it shows great promise as a prognostic marker of Type 2 diabetes mellitus. However, limited studies in India restrict its application in clinical

settings. Future studies should focus more on region-specific research to validate the personalised use of this bacterium in Type 2 diabetes mellitus in the Indian population.

1. Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder characterized by absolute or relative insulin resistance. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimated the global prevalence of type 2 DM to be 260 per 100,000 ^[1]. Complications of type 2 DM can induce gut dysbiosis. This causes decrease in the number of beneficial bacteria and induce inflammation, leading to insulin resistance. *Akkermansia muciniphila* (*Akk*) is a gram-negative anaerobic bacterium which is present as a commensal in the human gut. It stimulates the secretion of incretin hormones which stimulate insulin secretion from beta cells of pancreas. Studies by Liu et al (2019) and Sanjivani et al have shown that this bacterium reduces inflammation maintains microbiota homeostasis, and enhances intestinal barrier function in type 2 diabetes patients.^[2,3] The primary objective of this literature review is to assess the efficacy of *Akkermansia muciniphila* as a prognostic indicator in diabetes mellitus. The secondary objectives are to explore the impact of *Akkermansia muciniphila*, on glucose metabolism, intestinal barrier integrity, inflammatory pathways and insulin resistance in type 2 DM.

2. Current Gaps in Literature

2.1 Limited human clinical trials

- Most clinical trials use animals as the sampling population.
- Existing human trials often have small sample sizes and short durations(< 20 weeks) leading to bias in results.^[2]

2.2 Strain and Host Variability.

- There is significant genetic and phenotypic diversity among *A. muciniphila* strains leading to variability in outcomes

- Host factors such as gut microbiome composition affect bacterial colonization

2.3 Safety and Ethical Concerns

Regulatory approval and standardization of use of *A. muciniphila* is a major concern due to ethical guidelines

Methodology

Eligibility criteria:

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were identified based on a modified version of the PICO framework (**Population, Intervention, Control and Outcome**) to ensure a systematic and focussed approach to study selection.

Inclusion criteria

Population:

- Cross-sectional, case control and review articles sampling individuals with T2DM (FBS> 126 mg/dL, PPBS>200 mg/dL, HbA1c>6.5% ^[4]) according to the American Diabetes Association (ADA) criteria
- Studies using animals for clinical trials.

Intervention

- Studies involving culture of *A. muciniphila* on strictly anaerobic medium Brain Heart Infusion Medium (BHI)(37⁰C) , tryptophan soy broth
- Studies including genetic testing of 16s rRNA.

Outcome

Primary studies studying *A. muciniphila* as a prognostic marker of T2DM

Exclusion criteria**Population**

Studies not related to T2DM

Intervention

Studies involving culture of bacterium excluding *A. muciniphila*

Outcome

Studies having unclear outcome

Abbreviations

* FBS: Fasting blood sugar

* PPBS: Post-prandial blood sugar

* HbA1c: Glycated hemoglobin

Search strategy

A comprehensive search was conducted from 19/9/2025 to 28/10/2025 on databases such as PubMed, Cochrane and Semantic Scholar. In total, 1050 papers published from 2014 were identified, 349 were screened, 233 were deemed eligible, and the 20 most relevant were included in this review. Reasons for exclusion included unclear outcome (n=45), lack of full text (n=701), studies not related to T2DM (n=40) or *A. muciniphila* (n=20). The results of the study are highlighted in Table 1

Table 1: Search strategy

4. Discussion

4.1 Pathophysiology of gut dysbiosis and T2DM

T2DM is a metabolic disorder caused by insulin deficiency/resistance. This is caused by failure of pancreatic beta-cells failure to produce insulin; increased pancreatic alpha cell glucagon secretion; increased gluconeogenesis in liver; impaired insulin action in skeletal muscles; increased release free fatty acids (FFA) due to lipolysis from adipose tissue; deficiency of incretins (GLP-1) increased glucose reabsorption kidney through sodium-glucose cotransporters-2 (SGLT-2) in kidney and changes in the composition of the gut microbiota.^{[10][4] [5]}

Dysbiosis promotes insulin resistance due to the adherence of lipopolysaccharide (LPS) CD14 / toll-like receptor (TLR- 4 complex) on intestinal epithelial cells (IEC).^[6,7] It also causes endotoxemia (leakage of toxins) due to weakening of intestinal barrier. A study by Yu et al stated that shifts in the balance between Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes, a reduction in butyrate-producing bacteria (*A. muciniphila*), and an increase in opportunistic pathogens contributed to T2DM. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a common metabolic disorder characterized by insulin resistance and pancreatic β -cell dysfunction. Emerging evidence indicates that gut microbiota dysbiosis may contribute to the development of T2DM. Individuals with T2DM exhibit notable changes in gut microbiota composition, including shifts in the balance between Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes, a reduction in butyrate-producing bacteria, and an increase in

opportunistic pathogens. Gut microbiota-derived metabolites :such as short-chain fatty acids, bile acids, and amino acids: were implicated in the pathogenesis of T2DM, highlighting the critical role of host-microbe interactions. In this overview, we discussed the gut microbiota dysbiosis associated with T2DM and explore the molecular links between microbiota-derived metabolites and the pathogenesis of diseases. Additionally, we explore potential therapeutic strategies, including probiotics and dietary interventions, to modulate the gut microbiota and its metabolites, providing insights for future clinical research and the development of novel treatments for T2DM.^[7] The results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Interplay of dietary factors, T2DM and gut microbiota. Microbiota affects the host’s pathophysiological states by influencing 1) inflammation and immune response via the NF- κ

B pathway 2) β -cell function and insulin resistance, 3) Oxidation of (production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFA))^[8]

4.2 *A. muciniphila*: General characteristics

A. muciniphila is a gram-negative, non-spore-forming, non-motile bacterium belonging to phylum *Verrucomicrobia*. It consists of 1%–5% of the total intestinal bacteria.^[8] It grows on anaerobic culture media such as brain heart infusion (BHI) and tryptophan soy broth. It was discovered by Derrien et al in 2004 by combining culture medium such as anaerobic soft agar with 16S-RNA sequencing methods.^[9] Its multiple metabolic benefits include reduction of inflammation, improvement of liver function, reduction of lipotoxicity and modulation of gut permeability.

4.3 Mechanisms by which *A. muciniphila* reduces T2DM

Results of study by Yoon et al stated that *Akk* improved glucose homeostasis, by secreting protein P9 and inducing secretion of integrins like glucagon like peptide (GLP-1) ^[10,11] Study by Shaheen et al showed that *A. muciniphila* increased GLP-1 secretion via pathways producing SCFA (short chain fatty acids) and Toll-like receptor (TLR2) activation.^[11] SCFA's increased tight junctions like claudin and occludin in intestinal epithelial cells.

Studies also showed that *Akk* increased the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-10 in T2DM^[2,4,12–14] Chelakott et al (2016,) showed that *Akk*-derived extracellular vesicle therapy improved glucose tolerance in high-fat diet-induced diabetic mice by regulating gut permeability and enhancing intestinal barrier integrity.^[15] A study by Zhao et al showed that it reduced endoplasmic reticulum (ER) induced stress in liver and muscle cells.^[6]

4.4 Therapeutic outcomes on T2DM

A. muciniphila can be modulated via direct administration as a probiotic, administration of prebiotics and in combination with metformin or via bariatric surgery. Studies have shown that

administration of *A. muciniphila* in combination with prebiotics(oligofructose) in mice have improved its viability.^[16] Studies showed *Akk* species reduced obesity and improved metabolic outcomes.^[17-19] A meta-analysis by Liu et al showed that *Akk* reduced FBS by 21.2%, improved glucose tolerance by 22.1% and increased serum insulin levels by 26.9%. ($p < 0.001$) (Effect size 0.20 , 95%CI)^[2] A randomized control trial by Zhang et al (n=58) showed that use of *Akk* in T2DM patients caused reductions in body weight, fat mass, and HbA1c.^[18] A study by Depommier et al (2019) on obese/overweight insulin resistant volunteers for three months showed that pasteurized *Akk* improved insulin receptor sensitivity ($p = 0.002$), reduced insulinemia ($p = 0.006$), reduced body weight ($p = 0.091$), fat mass ($p = 0.092$) and plasma total cholesterol ($p = 0.02$); hip circumference ($p = 0.091$) compared to control group.^[19] A comprehensive summary of the key findings is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of included literature

Study/Population	Sample Size (Groups)	Intervention	Main Outcomes	Statistical Significance	Citation
Meta-analysis of animal studies	15 studies (varied, e.g., 6–24/group)	Akk supplementation, <20 wks	Decrease in Body weight by 10.4%, Increase in FBS by 21.2%, Increased glucose tolerance by 22.1% Increased insulin sensitivity by 26.9%	($p < 0.05$) pooled effect size for glucose: =0.18 (95% CI: 0.10–0.25)	[2]
Human RCT (overweight/obese, insulin-resistant)	40 enrolled (Placebo n=11, Pasteurized n=12, Live n=9)	3 months, 10^{10} CFU/day	Pasteurized bacteria showed Increased insulin sensitivity (28.6%) (P=0.002), decreased insulinemia (34.1%) (P=0.006), decreased cholesterol (8.7%) (P=0.02), decreased body weight – (P=0.091)	Significant for insulin sensitivity, insulinemia, cholesterol; weight loss trend	[20]
Human dietary intervention (obese adults)	49	6-week calorie restriction + 6-week stabilization	Higher baseline <i>A. muciniphila</i> : greater ↓ fasting glucose, triglycerides, body fat; improved insulin sensitivity	Wilcoxon, Kruskal-Wallis; ($p < 0.05$)	[18]
Human cross-sectional (lean/obese, T2D)	182 (4 groups: 22–56/group)	Observational	Increase in fasting glucose; correlation with FGF15/19	ANOVA (Analysis of variance) Spearman correlation coefficient; ($p < 0.01$)	[18]

5. Conclusion

Results of included studies showed that *A. muciniphila* has great promise as a prognostic marker of Type 2 diabetes mellitus. However, lack of studies involving humans as the cohort population are an issue. Future studies must be longitudinal in nature covering large scale multicentric populations. Including individuals from diverse age groups, genders, ethnic backgrounds will enhance the generalizability of the findings. These studies will offer novel directions and shape future prevention and treatment of metabolic diseases.

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Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest declared

Ethical clearance

The study is a narrative review and was based on previously published anonymized data. It did not involve human and animal trials. Hence ethical clearance was not required.

CRedit author statement

Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, data curation ,editing and writing

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